

Deployment of Federated Learning Infrastructure

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ABSTRACT

Federated Learning (FL) is a technique to train machine learning (ML) models on decentralized data, meaning the data is distributed across multiple devices. FL aids model managers in improving their ML models by training on large distributed data. It also enables privacy since local data is kept on clients' devices, and only model updates are shared. In an FL setting, two main types of entities exist the server and the client. Usually, there is one server and multiple clients, each having its local dataset. The server holds the global model, while the clients hold the data. In an FL training round, the server sends a copy of its global model to each client. The clients then train the received models on their local data and send the model weights back to the server, which are aggregated to update the global model. The process is repeated multiple times until the model achieves convergence. Sometimes, it is necessary to change training parameters and the network architecture to help the model converge. Such changes entail restarting the training process, which induces an overhead. In this project, we are developing a tool that automates the deployment of FL on multiple devices. The tool is built on top of existing FL frameworks and configuration tools. Several comparisons have been made to choose the best FL framework and configuration tool for our project. Details about the implementation and training flow description are provided in the following sections.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Federated learning (FL) is a machine learning technique that trains a model across multiple edge devices. Each device has its local dataset. The main idea is to utilize the data distributed across these devices and help improve model performance without accessing the actual data. In federated learning, a copy of the global model is sent to each device. These local models are trained on the local dataset. Once training is finished, the weights of these local models are sent back to the server. The weights from all devices are aggregated to update the global model. It is interesting to try out different parameters and strategies. However, manually redeploying all of that is time-consuming. Thus, in this project, we are trying to automate the deployment of federated learning by building an FL infrastructure that automatically deploys server and client programs. The infrastructure makes it possible to try out different aggregation algorithms, network architecture, and datasets.

2. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In an FL setting, there are a server and clients. The server holds the global model and sends it to the clients for training. The clients are responsible for training the model on their data samples and sending the weights of the resulting model to the server. The server aggregates the weights to update the global model. To simulate many clients, we deployed more than one client process on each of the client devices, as shown in Fig. 1. To isolate those client processes from the underlying

OS and allow for ease of deployment, we used containers. We also deployed a monitoring container to collect the training and evaluation metrics from the clients and the server and allow users to request these metrics at any time. In Fig. 1, one can see that there is another machine which is the control machine. This machine is responsible for deploying the client and the server containers using a configuration management tool. It also communicates with the monitoring container to get the evaluation metrics.

Before building our infrastructure, we need to decide which FL framework we will use, and which configuration tool is the best to deploy our system. In the following two sections, we will discuss this in more detail.

Figure 1 Federated Learning Workflow

3. FEDERATED LEARNING (FL) FRAMEWORKS

In this section, we briefly describe each of the existing FL frameworks, explore different metrics to evaluate, and compare them.

a. Existing FL frameworks

We will focus on nine frameworks: TensorFlow Federated (TFF), PySyft, Flower, Substra, FATE, IBM Federated, PaddleFL, OpenFL, and CAFIEN. Below are descriptions of each FL framework, how it works, and some of the features it supports.

i. TensorflowFederated

It is an open-source framework developed by Google on top of Tensorflow. It is mainly designed to facilitate open research and experimentation in federated learning. Its architecture consists of two main layers: the FL API and the Federated Core (FC). The FL API layer implements the federated training and evaluation. It also allows for designing custom federated learning algorithms. FC is a low-level framework below FL API which provides generic expressions and simulates custom computations. It has several extensions including Differential Privacy, Compression, and Quantization. It is also an architecture-agnostic platform, so it runs on any machine. In compilation, the code is converted into an abstract representation.

ii. PySyft

It is a PyTorch extension for secure and private deep learning. It is open-source and has a simple interface. It implements several algorithms related to secure aggregation like Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC). However, these features are still experimental and not for production use. Besides, it can work in a distributed environment using PyGrid.

iii. Flower

It is also an open-source and ML-framework agnostic framework. It supports TensorFlow, PyTorch, and other ML frameworks as well. It supports deployment to all types of devices, including mobile devices, AWS, GCP, Azure, Android, IOS, Raspberry Pi, and Nvidia Jetson. It supports usage in both production and research projects. Besides, it is a platform independent so it can run on different operating systems and heterogenous edge device environments. In addition, the package is well documented.

iv. Substra

It is an FL framework that supports distributed orchestration of ML tasks among collaborators. It is also an ML-Framework agnostic, so the data scientist can use his/her own ML algorithm. It allows training on remote datasets.

v. FATE

It is an open-source framework designed for enterprises and institutions. It implements secure computation protocols that are based on homomorphic

encryption and MPC. It supports different ML algorithms, including logistic regression, tree-based, deep learning, and transfer learning. It allows deployment on multiple nodes and has tools to be deployed using native technologies such as Docker Decompose and Kubernetes. It has a serving system for FL models, tools for visualization, MPC task scheduling platforms for the FL pipeline, an infrastructure for building and maintaining cloud services, a tool for optimizing and automating the configuration and deployment operations using Ansible, and an HPC framework for FL.

vi. IBM Federated

It is an ML-framework agnostic framework developed by IBM for federated learning. It supports different learning topologies like a shared aggregator. The framework is available in private and public clouds using either “Cloud Pak for Data” or “Cloud Pak for Data as a service.” However, Cloud Pak is not free. A community edition of IBM FL is well suited for academic users and researchers but not for production. This edition is available on GitHub as an open-source project. According to the GitHub repo, the platform supports neural networks, decision trees ID3, linear classifiers, linear regression, linear SVM, ridge regression, K-means, Naive Bayes, and logistic regression. It also supports Deep Reinforcement learning algorithms like DQN, DDPG, and PPO. Regarding the aggregation/fusion algorithms, it supports different algorithms for Neural Nets like Iterative Average, FedAvg, Gradient Average, PFNM, Krum, Coordinate-wise median, Zeno, Fed+, FedProx, and many others. For decision trees, it supports the ID3 fusion. It also implements fairness techniques to mitigate the bias in federated learning like Local Reweighting, Global Reweighting with DP, and Federated Prejudice Removal. The repo provides a notebook-based UI interface to aid the orchestration of FL experiments locally or even across remote machines. In addition, the framework automates the deployment of the aggregators and party process using the Multi-Cloud and Hybrid Cloud Orchestrator.

vii. PaddleFL

It is an open-source FL framework built on top of the PaddlePaddle ML framework. It only supports PaddlePaddle. However, it supports most of the technical features like deployment in large-scale distributed clusters. It provides several FL strategies with applications for CV, NLP, and recommendation systems. It supports both vertical and horizontal federated learning and MPC protocols like ABY3 and PrivC. They also have an FL-simulator extension to simulate the actual cooperated training online among multiple mobile terminal devices. It also uses Kubernetes to ease up the scheduling of training jobs. Although there is a documentation version of the documentation in English, most of the community is in Chinese, and that’s one of the main challenges for using PaddleFL.

PFL
Paddle Federated Learning

viii. OpenFL

Intel develops OpenFL framework. It is an ML-framework agnostic. DL frameworks like Tensorflow and PyTorch can be added via a plugin mechanism. It supports many aggregation algorithms like FedAvg, FedProx, FedOpt, and FedCurv. However, not all these algorithms have Tensorflow and PyTorch implementations. It also supports a lossy compression of data to reduce communication costs. In addition, OpenFL allows users to customize their logging, data split methods, and aggregation logic. It was meant to solve cross-silo FL problems. To enable secure communication, OpenFL uses certificates since communication between nodes in OpenFL is done using mTLS which makes certification necessary for each node. OpenFL has deployment

scripts written in bash, which requires the user to handle himself, which makes it a bit complicated to work with them.

ix. CAFIEN

It is a framework developed at CERN. It was created for the application of multi-institute brain MRI anomaly screening to assist clinicians, patients, and caregivers in the analysis and diagnosis of diseases based on the integration of clinical and patient data. The main problem with this framework is that it does not have many resources and is not open source.

b. FL System Characteristics

In order to compare federated learning frameworks, some characteristics are used like the FL framework's main concept: integrated or static, and its support of certain features like Differential Privacy, remote data loading, secure aggregation, and documentation quality. All these features are explained in detail below.

i. Support for real FL setting

In an FL environment, the client and the server are two different machines. The clients can be mobile devices, PCs, or IoT devices, while the server can be an instance on a remote machine. An FL framework must allow communication between devices to distribute the model to clients and aggregate model updates in the server. Some frameworks do not have support for this setting. They are used for simulation only where the clients and the server are within the same machine.

ii. Support of Machine Learning (ML) frameworks

The characteristic evaluates the compatibility of FL Frameworks to existing ML frameworks such as TensorFlow and PyTorch. It is an essential feature since it eases the conversion of standard ML systems to federated systems.

iii. Conceptual Design

FL frameworks are characterized by being either integrated or static. It measures how the system is designed to be integrated with ML frameworks and how this can affect system flexibility. Integrated Frameworks integrate very well with the existing ML frameworks. For example, TensorFlow Federated (TFF) integrates well with Tensorflow syntax. Tensorflow operations can be applied to remote data the same as to local data. PySyft also does the same with PyTorch. They use Remote Procedure Calls (RPCs) to invoke operations on remote data. The code is written on a single file that controls the computation of all clients, which enables fast development and adjustment of the code. However, the framework becomes limited by the operations provided by the ML framework.

On the other hand, Static Frameworks are based on the Multiple Program Multiple Data Paradigm. The logic and code are divided between the clients and the server. Each client gets an instruction file from the server to execute. It gives the client more independence and speed since the client does not rely on the supplement of instructions. It requires synchronization between the client and the server using event messages. However, it is more complicated since logic changes require communication with the clients to update their configurations.

iv. Support for remote data loading

This feature measures whether the framework supports loading and training on data that exists on the client's side, not uploaded by the server. In some frameworks, the server must distribute and upload the data, making it more suitable for research than production.

v. Support for IoT and mobile devices

It shows which type of devices can participate in the FL setting. Devices include Android mobile devices, IoT devices, iOS, and many others.

vi. Support for GPU acceleration

It shows whether the system can support model training on GPU.

vii. Support for the secure aggregation

Since model updates are transferred through the network, secure communication between the client and the server is needed. This feature shows the type of secure aggregation algorithms supported like MPC, Homographic Encryption.

viii. Support for Differential Privacy

This feature is intended to show whether the FL framework supports Differential Privacy or not.

ix. Documentation

This feature is intended to show the quantity and quality of documentation and whether there are enough code examples and tutorials to help beginners.

x. Community Support

This feature is added to show the FL framework's vitality and how much contribution it receives. It also indicates whether the framework development is active or not.

c. FL System Comparison

Framework	TFF	Pysyft	Flower	Substra
Conceptual Design	Integrated	Integrated	Static	Static
FL setting Sup.	Simulation only	Yes	Yes	Yes
ML framework	TensorFlow	PyTorch*	Any	Any
Remote Data Loading	No	Yes**	Yes	Yes
Supported Systems	Docker containers	Docker containers and mobile devices	OS and K8s (Docker Container), mobile, embedded, and internet of things devices	No mentioned
GPU Support	No	Yes	Yes	Not mentioned
Differential Privacy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not mentioned
Secure Aggregation	No	Yes	Under Development***	In perspective
Documentation	Basic Examples	Tutorial & examples in documentation and repository + blog posts and community projects	Tutorials / examples in documentation, boilerplate project examples in the repository	not so many examples
Community Support	Only developer documentation and stack overflow community support	Good documentation and good community support	Good documentation and good community support, e.g., through Slack	Good documentation. The community is not active. Repo is inactive

*The company website says there is support for TensorFlow as well, but there is no code example or tutorial to test this new feature.

**The website says it supports remote data loading, but there is no code example

***Still, no implementation exists for it. However, you can use a dedicated library for secure aggregation.

Framework	FATE	IBM Federated	PaddleFL	OpenFL
Conceptual Design	Static	Static	Static	Static
FL setting Sup.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
ML framework	Tensorflow*	Any including Keras, Pytorch, Tensorflow, Scikit-learn, and RLLib	PaddlePaddle	Any
Remote Data Loading	Data is uploaded to the nodes**	Yes	Yes	Yes
Supported Systems	Can only be implemented on Linux and windows. It uses Containers (Docker Compose and Kubernetes, (KubeFATE))	It uses Containers. It can be implemented on Linux and Windows. (Community Edition is not for production)	OS and K8s (Docker Container), mobile, embedded, and IoT devices	It's supported in PC, but there is no mention of using it for mobile devices
GPU Support	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Differential Privacy	Not mentioned	Yes	Yes	Not mentioned
Secure Aggregation	Yes	Implemented for some algorithms	Yes	Not mentioned
Documentation	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Community Support	Yes, there are but very basic in the documentation and repo	Yes, they have a lot of examples	Few examples in the repository and most of the community communicates in Chinese	Still Active

* Interestingly, the official FATE documentation states that PyTorch can be used; however, no related code can be found in the documentation. FATE not only implements NN, but it also implements regression models (linear, logistic, and Poisson) and a decision tree (gradient-boosting decision tree, GBDT).)

**Documentation says that the data should be uploaded to the nodes before deploying the clients. However, it does not mention anything whether the model can be trained on the local data without uploading it

d. Choosing the best framework

To choose the best framework, we begin by excluding frameworks. First, we excluded TFF since it is designed for simulation only. We also excluded PySyft since it only supports PyTorch now, FATE since it only supports TensorFlow, Substra since not enough information is given and the repo is inactive, IBM Federated since the community version is not for production use and there is not much code documentation, PaddleFL since it only works with PaddlePaddle ML Framework which is not a famous framework and most of the community is in Chinese, OpenFL since it is very complicated to deploy FL compared to other frameworks, CAFIEN since it is not open-source. Thus, we chose Flower since it supports any ML Framework, can be used in a real FL setting, and supports remote data loading, differential privacy, and GPU acceleration. It does not support Secure Aggregation, but libraries implementing secure aggregation can be plugged in. It has an active community and good documentation. It also allows deployment in different types of edge devices.

4. CONFIGURATION TOOLS

In order to deploy containers at the server and the client, we need a configuration tool to automate the deployment process and ease up trying different parameters and scenarios. In this section, we will briefly describe each of the existing configuration tools: Chef, Ansible, Puppet, and SaltStack. Then, we will describe the evaluation criteria and the comparison.

a. Orchestration Frameworks

i. Chef

It is an open-source program used for cloud configuration management and deployment automation. It translates system administration tasks into reusable definitions, also known as cookbooks and recipes. Chef has a client-server architecture. It runs on a variety of platforms like Windows and Linux. It can also be integrated with cloud platforms like AWS, Google Cloud Platform, and OpenStack. Chef provides hybrid and SaaS solutions for Chef Servers. It is very stable, reliable, and mature, especially for large deployments. However, the main problem with Chef is that it requires much learning besides its initial setup is somehow complicated.

ii. Puppet

Puppet is a configuration management tool that manages different clients from one server. It is also an open-source project under Apache License 2.0. Puppet has different advantages and disadvantages. It allows resource abstraction, so a system administrator does not have to remember all the commands and syntax of the individual platforms and operating systems. Instead, it uses a utility called Factor to know the system details like OS and IP address. Puppet is also cross-platform. It works on RHEL, Debian, Solaris, OS X, Windows, Gentoo, and Fedora. It has support for scheduling specific maintenance actions periodically. It also has an active community.

However, Puppet is written in Ruby, which is complex to understand and consequently hard to extend. Smaller setups are more suitable with other configuration tools. It also does not have comprehensive reporting features.

iii. Ansible

It is open-source software. It does not rely on a client-server model. It is a push-based configuration tool. Ansible control machines must be UNIX. Windows is not supported. Ansible has many advantages. It is easy to learn so it can increase beginners' productivity and makes troubleshooting a lot easier. It is written in Python, which is easy to read. There are also good facilities for running Ansible since Python exists in most Linux distributions. Ansible has modules that can be written in any language. In addition, Ansible has no dependency on the clients. It has an agentless nature. It uses the standard SSH to connect to the machines. Ansible Playbooks are written in YAML, a very easy language to read and develop. Since Ansible is new to the market, it does not have a large developer or user community like its competitors. It also does not have extensive enterprise support experience. However, it has a portal for reusing ansible-related content. Unlike Puppet, Ansible lacks any notion of state and does not track dependencies. It simply executes the sequential tasks and then stops if an error happens, or the task is finished.

iv. Saltstack

SaltStack is a configuration management framework like Chef, Puppet, and Ansible. It's based on the idea of executing commands remotely. In SaltStack terminology, the server is called the Master, and the clients are called the Minions. Commands are issued from the Master to a target group of Minions. Communication between the Master and the minions occurs over a bus called the ZeroMQ message bus. The Salt Master runs on Linux by default, but the minions can run on any OS. SaltStack offers Salt SSH, which provides agentless system management.

b. Configuration Tools Characteristics

i. Availability

It means there are multiple servers present. If the primary server goes down, a backup server will take place. All the tools mentioned above support multiple servers. Once the primary server goes down, another server takes place.

ii. Ease of Setup

It measures the easiness of installing these tools. Chef, SaltStack, and Puppet are not that easy since they have a master-agent architecture. A server and a client must be installed on the Master and the agent, respectively. Puppet also has a certificate that must be signed by the clients and the server, making installing it more complicated. On the other hand, Ansible is a master-only architecture, meaning there is only a program running on the server, no program on the clients. It uses SSH to connect to the nodes and control them. That makes it easy since the clients do not need any setup.

iii. Management

There are two types of management types: pull and push. In the pull configuration, the clients pull the configurations from the server. In push one, the server pushes the configurations

to the clients. Chef and Puppet are pull-based configuration tools, while Ansible and SaltStack are push-based.

iv. Configuration Language

Chef uses Ruby DSL to write configurations while Puppet uses its language Puppet DSL, which is not easy to manage. Ansible and Saltstack use YAML, which is a very easy language, very similar to English.

v. Scalability

It describes whether the tools support a large number of nodes. It turns out that all the tools are highly scalable.

vi. Interoperability

In all the tools, the server must be UNIX. However, the clients can be windows or Linux.

c. Comparison between Frameworks

Framework	Ansible	Chef	Puppet	SaltStack
Availability	Multiple Servers	Multiple Servers	Multiple Servers	Multiple Servers
Ease of Setup	Easy	Difficult	Difficult	Difficult
Management	Push Configuration (Easy)	Pull Configuration (Not that easy)	Pull Configuration (Not that easy)	Push Configuration (Easy)
Scalability	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Configuration Language	YAML	Ruby DSL	Puppet DSL	YAML
Interoperability	Server on UNIX, Client on Any	Server on UNIX, Client on Any	Server on UNIX, Client on Any	Server on UNIX, Client on Any

d. Why Ansible?

We can see that Ansible is the best among the other configuration tools since it allows multiple servers, is easy to set up, is easy to learn, and allows push configuration. It is also scalable and interoperable.

5. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

In this section, we are trying to give more technical details about the project and how it is implemented.

a. Environment Setup

To create a federated learning setting, I requested four instances from CERN OpenStack: one for the server and the others for the clients. The instances have CentOS 7 installed with four virtual CPUs, 7.3 GB of RAM, and 40 GB of hard disk. For initial experimentation, I installed Tensorflow and Flower using conda on each machine and ran a basic example from Flower. It trains a MobileNet model on the MNIST dataset. The example uses the FedAvg strategy to aggregate the updates. During my experimentation, I discovered that the client and the server could not communicate because of the standard firewall. To solve the problem, I opened the specific ports on each machine to allow communication.

b. Containerization

Docker was used to building containers for both the client and the server. Two main Dockerfile scrips were used for each with a TensorFlow pre-image. Flower package was installed using pip on top of TensorFlow. To allow the python process to communicate with the outside network and thus communicates with the server, the port mapping of (8080:8080) is used. Afterward, Docker containers were deployed on each of the four CentOS instances: one for the server and the other three for the clients. I created shell scripts to build, load the images in containers, and remove them at the end. At this stage, several implementations were made. In previous trials, I created an overlay network to connect the server and the clients, but it was difficult to open ports while the firewall was running, so I used the standard networks.

c. Deployment Automation

In order to automate the deployment of containers, I used Ansible. I have created four main Ansible playbooks.

1. Install Requirements
 - a. Install Docker, pip, and Docker-ce on all machines, both server, and clients
2. Server/Client/Monitor run (separate)
 - a. Remove previous server/client/monitor containers on the specific instance
 - b. Send the source files for the server/client/monitor program from the control machine to the instance
 - c. Build the image on the instance
 - d. Load the container and run it there

Let us describe the motivation behind the monitor server. Since transferring metrics is hard, we used another process/container to receive the evaluation metrics from the clients and the server and send them to the user if requested. That way, we can ensure the metrics are available even if the clients and the server finish training.

6. RESOURCES

The tool is implemented in two python packages: *fed_deploy* and *fed_pack*.

a. Fed_deploy

This package is responsible for containerizing the client and the server programs into Docker containers and deploying them using Ansible.

GitHub Link: https://github.com/mashrafhemdan1/fed_deploy

b. Fed_pack

This package imports certain libraries inside the containers to be used by the FL programs. For example, it imports Tensorflow, and Flower to be used in the client and the server programs. It is required by the *fed_deploy* package and automatically installed by the *fed_deploy* package inside the Docker containers.

GitHub Link: https://github.com/mashrafhemdan1/fed_pack

